

HISTORY OF THE STUDY OF HISTORICAL AND ARCHAIC LEXICAL UNITS IN WORLD LINGUISTICS

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Abstract: *Problems related to the study of historical and archaic lexical units have always been the focus of attention of linguists, scholars, translators, and other scientists who are conducting research in a number of similar fields. Even now, the research of archaic and historical lexical units is of great importance in modern linguistics.*

Key words: *historical words, archaic words, lexical units, ancient words, obsolete objects, historicism, archaism, modern language, semantic archaisms, original lexicon.*

Each word certainly has its own history of origin. Some words completely disappear from our daily life, and some remain, despite being rarely used. Ancient words can be divided into two groups: archaic words (archaism) and historical words (historicism). Historical words are mainly the names of things, and these words are lexical units that have been forgotten over time and are no longer in use today. Archaic lexical units are the names of obsolete objects and concepts, which today are called by other names for some reason. For example Uzbek archaic words such as *o'rdu-qo'shin* (army), *handasa-geometriya* (geometry), *tilmoch-tarjimon* (interpreter), *mirza-kotib* (secretary), *sadr-ra'is* (chirman), *lak-yuz ming* (hundred thousand) are archaic words that express the spirit of their time.

The difference between historical words (also known as historicism) and archaism is that today that historical reality itself does not have another lexical unit meaning it, so historicism is the only name of the phenomenon it represents. For example, when words such as *amin*, *pristav*, *mingboshi*, *nayib*, *elikboshi* are used in a literary text, the reader brings to mind the historical reality related to the social management system.

The term archaism is derived from the ancient Greek (*archaïkós*, *archaïkós*—meaning old, ancient), and the obsolete form of the language is called archaic. Although this term dates back to about 1751, it still does not have a precise definition.

French linguist J. Maruzo gave a general definition of archaisms in his dictionary of linguistic terms. According to him, archaisms are a specific form of language structure, words belonging to a period earlier than the one in which they are used. Some linguists take archaisms out of the scope of the modern language system and describe them as unreal existing units of a given language. Only elements that are outside the modern norm are rated as obsolete. Other researchers, on the contrary, considered archaisms as modern language elements. This is because they did not perform this task in other periods. To achieve some effect or as part of some slang archaisms can be used in formula or in religious contest. The process of word obsolescence can be divided into three stages: 1) words are rarely used; 2) words gradually falling out of use; 3) stages of unrecognizability of archaic words in modern language. For example, such words were used during the Old English period, but by today, the form of these words has changed so much that they have become unrecognizable [losso = lazy fellow- a lazy person].

It is known that archaisms serve to give a pompous tone to the poetic speech, to increase the effectiveness. From this point of view, in his works, Navoi also referred to the lexical elements and grammatical language forms characteristic of the East Turkestan language. In Navoi's works, we also find several lexical archaisms: kamuk - all. This word is also found in the writings of Urhun-Enasai, "Kutadgu bilig", Mahmud Kashgari dictionary, Rabguzi, "Nakhulfarodis", "Muhabbatnama".

If we look at the recent past, we can also find historical and archaic lexical units in the works of great artists such as Fitrat, Behbudi, Cholpon, Qahhor, Oybek, Gafur Ghulam, Hamid Olimjon, Abdulla Qadiri. In fiction, archaisms are widely used as a stylistic tool to polish speech, reflect the appearance of the era, and also for satirical purposes. From archaism in Russian literature M.E. Shchedrin ("Istoriya odnogo gorod"), A. Pushkin ("Eugene Onegin", "Boris Godunov"), Mayakovsky ("Oblako v shtanax"), M. Lermontov ("Demon"), A.N. Tolstoy ("Pyotr Pervy"), Yu.N. Tynyanov ("Kyukhlya") and others widely used. The first use of archaic lexical units in English literature can be found in "The Canterbury Tales" by Dj. Chaucer in the 14th century.

However, in the works which were published after 1755 archaic words were used more vividly. S.T. Coleridge, W. Shakespeare ("Twelfth Night"), E. Hemingway ("For Whom the Bell Tolls"), Edgar A. Poe ("The Raven") and Robert Frost ("The Road Not Taken") are considered to be vivid manifestations of archaism. Despite the fact that archaic lexical units and historical words are leaving our everyday life, they should not be completely forgotten, because they give a historical color to the text. The need to refer to an outdated dictionary usually arises in the authors of scientific and historical works. Sometimes, even in formal communication, obsolete words are used. For

example, in some legal documents in Russian there are such words (деяние, кара, возмездие, содеянное), at other times such words are considered archaisms. Indian scholar L. Chauhan in his article "The use of archaic language in jurisprudence" states that the use of archaic words has become a habit among jurists, especially lawyers, and it has become a symbol of the lawyer's style. According to Chauhan, lawyers do this on purpose so that ordinary people cannot understand the letters and documents they write without their help. "...lawyer's profession depends on language. The more skillfully he uses the structure and grammar of the language, the more he will benefit, the general belief prevails that only a lawyer can understand and communicate with another lawyer," says the scientist.

In our country, certain laws and regulations are followed when drafting normative legal documents. The regulatory document must be written in purely literary language, strictly following grammatical rules. In order to avoid misunderstandings in the future, it is not allowed to deviate from the generally accepted forms of literary language. Since language is a constantly evolving phenomenon, the meaning of words can change. Therefore, it is necessary to strictly observe the rule that provides for the use of words and terms in the meaning of the normative document at the time of its adoption. It is not possible to use words and sentences belonging to the local dialect or obsolete (archaic) words. Because the normative document is a means of regulation of social relations, influence of the authorities on human behavior. Unlike a work of art, it appeals not to people's feelings and imagination, but to their will and intelligence.

As we can see, the use of archaic words is carried out in different countries, in different fields, based on certain rules, laws, settled thoughts, customs. Any language changes over time. The development of society, cultural development, the creation of new technological tools, the formation of new ideas about the world stimulate the emergence of new objects and concepts expressed in words. In such cases, words emerge that reflect these new concepts. Such words are called neologisms. New words appear, and some lexical units become past tense, not used in speech. Such words are called archaisms.

Although archaic lexical units are widely used in fiction, it is not recommended to use them in writing poems (poetry), otherwise readers may not fully understand the meaning of the poem. However, for some categories of texts, archaisms are perfectly acceptable, even necessary. Among them are works written on historical and religious topics. In such cases, skillfully used archaism allows the author to more accurately describe events, objects, actions or feelings.

Archaisms can be divided into three classes based on lexical and grammatical classifications.

- a) lexical archaic units;
- b) semantic archaisms - words that reflect the outdated meaning of the word;
- c) grammatical archaisms - grammatically changed words.

Lexical archaic units are further divided into several types:

- 1) original lexicon - completely obsolete words;
- 2) lexical-phonetic - words that differ from modern words by several sounds;
- 3) lexical-morphological - words that differ from modern words by certain grammatical signs;
- 4) word-former - words that differ by the characteristic of word-formation (often through a suffix);
- 5) accentological - words separated by accent.

This classification is appropriate in translation, it allows to correctly distribute the archaisms found in the original text to the given groups.

Thus, summarizing the results of the studies analyzed above allows us to propose the following tariff for archaism.

Archaisms are words that for some reason have fallen out of the colloquial speech, sometimes replaced by other words (synonyms), which represent realities and things that existed in the past.

Linguists advise not to confuse archaisms with historicisms. If not only the word, but also the phenomenon represented by this word is obsolete, then this is a historicism or a historical unit.

According to other scholars, historicisms are a type of archaisms. If we rate archaisms from this point of view, archaisms are obsolete and obsolete words or names of obsolete and obsolete things and events left in history.

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